

Institutional Theory: Trajectory of eGovernment Initiatives in Indonesia

Kholid Haryono^{a}, Beni Suranto^b, Rafal Kusa^c*

^a Universitas Islam Indonesia, Department of Informatics, Yogyakarta, Indonesia,
e-mail: kholid.haryono@uii.ac.id, ORCID: 0000-0003-1859-0929

^b Universitas Islam Indonesia, Department of Informatics, Yogyakarta, Indonesia,
e-mail: beni.suranto@uii.ac.id, ORCID: 0000-0001-6865-8157

^c AGH University of Krakow, Faculty of Management, Gramatyka 10, 30-067 Krakow, Poland,
e-mail: rkusa@agh.edu.pl, ORCID: 0000-0002-9819-897X

* Corresponding author: Kholid Haryono, e-mail: kholid.haryono@uii.ac.id

Acknowledgements

The publication was co-financed by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1); Project number: 101086381; Project title: Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia.

Abstract

Objective: Institutional theory has been widely used in research on ICT and its implementation in eGovernment topics, yet the implementation from an institutional initiative perspective has not received much attention. To enhance the implementation perspective, this study employs three concepts within the theory as analytical lenses: institutional isomorphism, institutional logic, and institutional entrepreneurship. The aim is to understand the relationships between roles and initiatives in the journey of governmental digital transformation from the perspective of state institutions.

Method: This study employs an interpretive case study approach to examine the process of eGovernment initiatives in Indonesia from 2018 to 2022. The data is interpreted using institutional theory as the lens for analysis.

Result: e-Government maturity in Indonesia is measured using the CMMI technique. During the period 2018 - 2022, the measurement results show its influence on increasing Indonesia's EGDI index as measured by the UN. The initiatives carried out by the government through SPBE have succeeded in achieving increased digital transformation in government institutions.

Keywords: e-Government, digital transformation, Indonesia, Institutional Theory

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of information and communication technology (ICT) has significantly influenced the governance practices of nations worldwide. The United Nations e-Government Development Index (EGDI) provides a benchmark to evaluate the progress of e-Government initiatives globally (Wijaya, 2023). Indonesia, as a developing country, has demonstrated a growing commitment to improving its e-Government systems through various initiatives, such as the Electronic-Based Government System (Sistem Pemerintahan Berbasis Elektronik, SPBE) (Rusmini et al., 2024). However, the country still faces challenges in achieving higher rankings on the EGDI, which is often attributed to issues such as inadequate infrastructure, lack of standards, and insufficient public engagement (El gohary, 2017). This study investigates the trajectory of Indonesia's e-Government initiatives and examines their impact on the EGDI.

The primary focus of this study is the implementation of the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) in Indonesia. SPBE represents a comprehensive effort by the Indonesian government to modernize its governance through the adoption of digital technologies (Rusmini et al., 2024). Institutional theory serves as the theoretical framework for this analysis, particularly emphasizing institutional isomorphism, institutional logic, and institutional entrepreneurship (Meyer & Rowan, 2011; Wahid & Sein, 2014). By applying this framework, this study aims to understand how institutional dynamics shape the design and implementation of e-Government initiatives in Indonesia, as well as the role of transparency and public participation in enhancing these initiatives (Sabani, 2021).

The study addresses the following research questions:

1. What are the initiatives made by the Indonesian government?
2. How is the e-Government index in Indonesia measured?
3. How does each measurement indicator in the EGDI relate to the SPBE initiatives?
4. How does institutional theory explain the influence of these initiatives on the EGDI?

The findings of this study contribute to the understanding of how e-Government initiatives are formulated and evaluated in the context of a developing nation. Moreover, it provides insights into the interplay between institutional dynamics and e-Government outcomes, particularly in relation to EGDI measurements (Rusmini et al., 2024). The importance of aligning e-Government initiatives with local contexts and stakeholder needs is crucial for their success (Rachmawati & Dwi Fitriyanti, 2021).

To aid readers in comprehending the results of this study, the paper is systematically organized into six sections. Following this introduction, the Theoretical Background section elaborates on institutional theory and its relevance to e-Government studies. The Research Methodology section outlines the approach used to collect and analyze data. The Results section presents the key findings, while the Discussion section interprets these findings in the context of the research questions and theoretical framework. Finally, the Conclusion section summarizes the contributions of this study and provides recommendations for future research and policy development.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. e-Government

E-government, as an evolving concept, has been defined by various scholars from different perspectives. Jane Fountain (2001) defines it as the use of information and communication technologies, especially the internet, by government agencies to transform their relationships with citizens, businesses, and other government institutions. Ake Grönlund (2005) views e-government as a means for governments to use the most innovative information and communication technologies, particularly internet-based applications, to provide easier access for citizens and businesses to government information and services (Grönlund & Horan, 2005). According to Stephen Goldsmith and William D. Eggers (2004), e-government encompasses digital interactions between government and citizens (G2C), government and business/commercial entities (G2B), government and employees (G2E), as well as among government units and agencies (G2G). Rowena Cullen (2009) emphasizes improving the accessibility of government services and information for citizens, promoting a more citizen-centered approach and transparency in governance processes. Marc Holzer and Seang-Tae Kim (2007) define e-government as the use of the Internet and the world-wide-web to deliver government information and services to citizens. Layne and Lee (2001) offer an evolutionary perspective, suggesting that e-government evolves through four stages: catalog, transaction,

vertical integration, and horizontal integration. The UN-DESA E-Government Survey (2022) defines e-government as the use of information and communication technologies, particularly the internet, to enhance the activities of public sector organizations.

These definitions collectively depict e-government as encompassing a broad range of activities, from delivering online services to enhancing citizen engagement and intergovernmental collaboration, reflecting technological advancements and the expanded scope of government activities in the digital realm. In the context of this research, e-Government is also referred to as the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE), which is the administration of government utilizing information and communication technology to provide services to SPBE users (Presidential Regulation 95, 2018). In this definition, SPBE users are described as Central Agencies, Regional Governments, Civil Servant employees, individuals, communities, business actors, and other parties utilizing SPBE services.

2.2. Institutional Theory

Institutional Theory, as a significant perspective in organizational theory, has been extensively explained by various scholars. W. Richard Scott, in his book "Institutions and Organizations" (1995), defines institutions as social structures that have achieved a high level of resilience, characterized by three main pillars: regulative (rules and laws), normative (values and norms), and cultural-cognitive (conceptions and shared meanings)(Scott, 2014). This perspective aligns with the theory's origins in sociology and anthropology in the late 19th century. Émile Durkheim, a French sociologist, and Max Weber, a German sociologist, were instrumental in shaping the early ideas. Durkheim's concept of social facts and Weber's analysis of bureaucracy laid the groundwork for understanding how social structures influence individual actions. In the early 20th century, economic influences entered through Thorstein Veblen, an American economist and sociologist, who also played a role in the early development of Institutional Theory. He critiqued classical and neoclassical economic theories, emphasizing the importance of social and cultural factors in economic behavior.

Beginning in the 1970s, Institutional Theory evolved more systematically into organizational analysis, marked by the emergence of the concept of Institutional Isomorphism. Paul J. DiMaggio and Walter W. Powell (1983), who introduced this concept, explain how organizational fields become homogenized over time through coercive, mimetic, and normative isomorphism (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Wahid & Sein, 2014). Coercive Isomorphism stems from political influence and legitimacy issues. It encompasses formal and informal pressures exerted on organizations by other organizations they depend on and by cultural expectations in the society in which they operate. This often occurs in the form of enforced standard operational procedures and legitimate rules and structures by more powerful entities, such as governments or major donors. Mimetic Isomorphism results from the standard organizational response to uncertainty about what actions to take. In such conditions, organizations look for models or examples deemed successful or legitimate to emulate. Normative Isomorphism, related to professionalization, arises from the tendency to imitate organizations that hold high reputation or status in a field through benchmarking, training, professional mentoring, and academic activities (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983). Meyer and Rowan (1977), in "Institutionalized Organizations: Formal Structure as Myth and Ceremony," argue that organizations comply with social expectations and myths, often ceremonially adopted to gain legitimacy, rather than for efficiency reasons(Meyer & Rowan, 2011).

Organizational perspective shifts are also influenced by the foundational beliefs underpinning organizational change, known as Institutional Logic. Thornton, Ocasio, and Lounsbury (2012) in "The Institutional Logics Perspective: A New Approach to Culture, Structure, and Process" elaborate on Institutional Logic as a system of beliefs and related practices that direct and give meaning to organizational behavior within an institutional context

(Thornton et al., 2015). Hence, culture plays a crucial role. Such behavior is influenced by agency, cognitive, and social structures within the institution, especially by actors possessing an entrepreneurial spirit (Thornton et al., 2015). Howard E. Aldrich and Ruef Martin (2006) in "Organizations Evolving" discuss Institutional Entrepreneurship, defining it as the activities of actors who utilize resources to create new institutions or transform existing ones (Aldrich & Ruef, 2006). This concept relates to the idea of change agents playing a critical role in institutional change and innovation. Nonetheless, Friedland and Alford (1991) argue that to understand actor behavior, such behavior must be placed within an institutional context that governs behavior and provides opportunities for agency and change.

2.3. Institutional Theory in e-Government

Institutional Theory has evolved from the fields of sociology and economics to encompass various domains, including governance. Peter Frumkin (2004) presents a comparison of the resilience of government institutions versus other business or nonprofit organizations, noting that government institutions are still weak in facing coercive, normative, and mimetic pressures (Frumkin, 2004). Fathul Wahid (2012) used institutional isomorphism, institutional logic, and institutional entrepreneurship to explain how the adoption of e-procurement in developing countries occurs. He successfully demonstrated the influence of actors and policies taken, which have improved the corruption perception index (CPI) (Wahid & Sein, 2013, 2014). Chizema & Pogrebna (2019) employed Institutional Theory to understand the impact of government integrity and culture on leadership practices (Chizema & Pogrebna, 2019). From field studies, Chizema found that government integrity has a positive causal effect on the corporate governance decisions and choices made by business leaders. From an institutional perspective, human and social behavior is influenced by country-level institutions such as norms, routines, and historical patterns. These factors determine isomorphism among individuals and organizations (Chizema & Pogrebna, 2019; DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Scott, 2001, 2014). In Korea, Institutional Theory was used to analyze the appointment of an external director or professional in state-controlled companies. The results showed significant progress and a positive influence on corporate development (Chizema & Kim, 2010). Based on these studies, this theory is suitable for use as an analytical lens for examining the journey of e-government in Indonesia and elucidating how the elements involved in e-government over the years have influenced the achievement of improvements in e-government.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. The Context

In 2022, Indonesia achieved an EGDI score of 0.7160, ranking 77th out of 193 United Nations member states. This marks an improvement from the previous measurement in 2020, where Indonesia scored 0.6612, ranking 88th, and from 2018, with a score of 0.5258, ranking 107th. This improvement is attributed to various initiatives undertaken by the Indonesian government. One such initiative is the issuance of Presidential Regulation Number 95 of 2018 on Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE). This initiative focuses on four main domains: policy, governance, management, and services. The initial policy implemented was the formation of a national SPBE team that coordinates all e-Government initiatives in Indonesia. The team's roles consist of Chief Information Officer (CIO), Chief Information Security Officer (CISO), Research and Development (R&D), Chief Financial Officer (CFO), Chief Data Officer (CDO), Chief Technology Officer (CTO), and Chief Process Officer (CPO).

The initiative for accelerating digital transformation primarily began with bureaucratic reform, focusing on bureaucracy that directly impacts the public, a digital bureaucracy not reliant on paper, and an agile and fast bureaucracy. These three initiatives are related to the EGDI, which consists of three measurements: the Online Service Index (OSI),

Telecommunication Infrastructure Index (TII), and Human Capital Index (HCI). Therefore, one of the expected impacts of the SPBE initiative is an increase in EGDI scores and rankings. To realize this improvement, Indonesia has broken down the four domains into eight aspects: the Aspect of internal policy governance of SPBE, Strategic planning aspect, Information, and communication technology aspect, SPBE implementation aspect, SPBE management application aspect, ICT audit aspect, Government administration service aspect, and Electronic-based public service aspect. To ensure that all domains and aspects are progressing towards sustainable improvement, the government conducts an annual assessment of all Central Government Institutions and Regional Governments (IPPD). By 2022, the number of assessed IPPDs had reached 99.41%, which is 544 out of 620 IPPDs. Consists of 34 ministries, 26 LPNK, 34 provinces, 397 districts, 93 city governments, and 36 other institutions that are responsible to the president or ministries.

The government, through the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform (Menpan RB), issued the SPBE governance initiative as an implementation of Presidential Regulation 95, with the issuance of Menpan RB Regulation No. 5 of 2018 on Guidelines for the Evaluation of the Electronic-Based Government System. This regulation was updated through Menpan RB Regulation No. 59 of 2020. Through these regulations, all IPPDs must prepare for the institutional process of digital transformation through SPBE in two capabilities: process capability and service capability (technical). These two capabilities are measured using the maturity model method derived from the Capability Maturity Model/CMM Integration and the E-Government Maturity Model. The CMMI is a model released by the Software Engineering Institute (SEI), originally used to measure the maturity level of software development processes. Over time, this model has also been used in various fields such as the maturity level of ICT governance by COBIT, enterprise architecture, risk management, knowledge management, data management, and information security management (ISACA, 2012). The E-Government Maturity Model is a model used to measure the maturity stages of ICT service development. This model was developed by (Layne & Lee, 2001), (Andersen & Henriksen, 2006), (Kim & Grant, 2010), and the United Nations in the UN e-Government Survey (2022)(UN-DESA Survey, 2022).

The process capability level is a measurement of organizational maturity in SPBE policy, governance, and management capabilities. The maturity level uses five stages, labeled 1 – 5, starting from the pioneering level, managed, defined, integrated, and measured, to the optimum level. Similarly, the service capability level also employs five stages, with the capability levels progressing from the information level, interaction, transaction, collaboration (integration), to the highest, which is the optimum level.

The structure of the SPBE maturity level is divided into three components: domain, aspect, and indicator. The domain represents the area of SPBE application and is divided into four: 1) internal policy, 2) governance, 3) management, and 4) service. The aspect refers to more specific areas within SPBE application and consists of 8 aspects: 1) internal policy governance, 2) strategic planning, 3) information and communication technology, 4) SPBE implementation, 5) management application, 6) execution of ICT audits, 7) government administration services, and 8) public services. The indicator is even more detailed as it contains specific information for each aspect of SPBE implementation. There are 47 indicators under the aspect structure. This structure is illustrated in the figure 1.

Figure 1. Indicators under the aspect structure

The weighting of the maturity measurement is divided into three levels: the SPBE index, domain index, and aspect index. The calculation of the SPBE index is an aggregate of the domains or aspects. The weight assigned to each domain and aspect is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The weight of domain and aspect

Domain	Aspect	Name of Domain or Aspect	Weight
1	1	Internal policy of SPBE	13,0
	1	Internal governance policy of SPBE	13,0
2	2-4	Governance of SPBE	25,0
	2	Strategic planning of SPBE	10,0
	3	Information and Communication Technology (ICT)	10,0
	4	Organizer of SPBE	5,0
3	5-6	Manajement of SPBE	16,5
	5	Implementation and Management of SPBE	12,0
	6	Implementation of ICT Audits	4,5
4	7-8	Services of SPBE	45,5
	7	Electronic Based Government Administration Services	27,5
	8	Electronic Based Public Services	18,0

The SPBE index maturity level calculation is calculated based on the formula:

$$Indeks\ Domain_i = \frac{1}{BD_i} \sum_{j=m}^n NA_{ij} \times BA_{ij}$$

Where:

- Domain Index is the index value, namely 1, 2, 3, and 4.
- BD_i is the weight of the domain from i to j
- NA_{ij} is the aspect value from i to j
- BA_{ij} is the aspect weight from i to j

The capability predicates derived from the SPBE index measurement results are divided into five categories: 'Satisfactory' with a score of 2.3 – 5.0; 'Very Good' with a score of 3.5 – 4.2; 'Good' with a score of 2.6 – 3.5; 'Adequate' with a score of 1.8 – 2.6; and 'Insufficient' with a score of < 1.8. The national SPBE index achievements for the years 2018-2021 received an 'Adequate' predicate, and in 2022, it improved to be 'Good'. The journey of digital transformation by the Indonesian government through SPBE has been proven to positively influence the improvement of the EGDI. How this influence occurs and how institutionally this

initiative is implemented are questions that will be answered in this research. This study uses institutional theory as an analytical lens to explain how the journey of digital transformation is carried out by the government from the perspective of the institutions implementing SPBE. Analysis is conducted on data over a five-year period, from 2018 to 2022.

3.2. Research Method

The approach used in this research is naturalistic interpretivism. This method was introduced by Klein and Myers, who stated that reality can be understood through social constructions such as language-based communication, consciousness, shared and interpreted meanings, documents, tools, and artifacts (Klein & Myers, 1999). This approach is suitable for research where the researcher is involved and participates directly in the process of the object being studied. In this context, the researcher has been one of the SPBE assessors from the university sector for three years, from 2021 to 2023.

The data for this research was obtained through various forms and methods, including from the annual reports of the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform, which acts as the coordinator and authority holder for SPBE management. Among its authorities, it conducts SPBE monitoring and evaluation activities annually, and this data was collected over a five-year period from 2018 to 2022. In addition to documents, data was also obtained through socialization, workshops, and assessor training conducted annually from 2021 to 2023. These activities facilitated the researcher in understanding the data obtained and its context in relation to this research, namely alignment with efforts to improve Indonesia's EGDI. The researcher also actively participated in FGDs with five assessors in a forum for harmonizing perceptions and understanding of SPBE monitoring and evaluation data over the years (Edmunds, 1999). Data was also derived from the verification process through interviews between the researcher and the IPPDs under their responsibility (Creswell, 2014). Over three years, interviews and verifications were conducted with 12 central institutions and 20 regional governments at the provincial, district, and city government levels. Each interview and verification lasted 100-120 minutes for each IPPD. Every year, the researcher was involved at least twice in presenting the progress and results of SPBE monitoring and evaluation among university assessors. Presentation notes at least provided data from ten assessors, with each presenting between 4 to 8 IPPDs. All activities conducted, from collecting documents in the form of reports to the monitoring and evaluation processes, helped reduce the researcher's personal bias and strengthen the objectivity of interpretations in this research. After the data was collected and organized periodically, analysis was then conducted.

The analytical lens used in this research is institutional theory (Aksom & Tymchenko, 2020). It comprises three theories: institutional isomorphism, institutional logic, and institutional entrepreneurship. Institutional isomorphism is employed to identify factors influencing IPPDs in carrying out digital transformation processes within their respective institutions. Institutional logic is used for analyzing the reasons and philosophical factors driving IPPDs in the digital transformation process. Meanwhile, institutional entrepreneurship is utilized to understand how leadership and the courage of individuals within IPPDs influence the pace of the digital transformation journey.

4. Results

The results of the national SPBE index measurements over a five-year period are presented in the following Table 2.

Table 2. The national SPBE index measurements

Description	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Index SPBE of National	1,98	2,18	2,26	2,24	2,34

Index of Policy Domain	1,75	1,95	2,07	2,21	2,39
Index of Governance Domain	1,74	1,86	1,95	1,89	1,85
Index of Manajement Domain	-	-	-	1,23	1,32
Index of Services Domain	2,17	2,40	2,48	2,81	2,96
Total of IPPD in "Good" level	82	196	256	159	234
Total of IPPD assessed	582	603	603	517	620

During the years 2018-2020, the assessment utilized the instrument from Permenpan RB No. 5 of 2018, which did not account for the management domain. Subsequently, the updated Permenpan RB No. 59 of 2020 was used, which had been refined with additional initiatives as improvements to complete the system. As a result, in 2021, the national SPBE index decreased by 0.2. The annual changes in the index numbers are inseparable from various initiatives and activities spearheaded by the national SPBE team. The development of these initiatives is shown in Table 3.

Below is a table of Indonesia's EGDI indicators.

Table 3. Indonesia's EGDI indicators

2022 Indonesia EGDI	2014	2016	2018	2020	2022
E-Government Development Index rank	106	116	107	88	77
E-Government Development Index value	0.44874	0.44784	0.52580	0.66120	0.71600
E-Participation Index rank	110	114	92	57	37
E-Participation Index value	0.29411	0.37288	0.61800	0.75000	0.71590
Online Service Index value	0.36220	0.36232	0.56940	0.68240	0.76440
Telecommunication Infrastructure Index value	0.30544	0.30158	0.32220	0.56690	0.63970
Human Capital Index value	0.67860	0.67960	0.68570	0.73420	0.74380

The data shows a consistent improvement in Indonesia's EGDI (E-Government Development Index) over recent years. In 2016, Indonesia's EGDI value was 0.4478, placing the country at rank 116 globally. By 2018, the value had risen to 0.5258, improving its rank to 107. This upward trend continued in 2020 with an EGDI value of 0.6612, positioning Indonesia at rank 88. Most recently, in 2022, the EGDI value reached 0.7160, propelling Indonesia to rank 77. This steady progression reflects significant advancements in the country's e-government initiatives, particularly in online services and participation. Notably, this improvement is a direct result of Indonesia's efforts in implementing the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE), which has enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of public service delivery while aligning with international e-government standards.

The comparison between Indonesia's SPBE Index and the EGDI over the years 2018 to 2022 suggests a positive correlation between the government's initiatives through SPBE and the country's improvement in the EGDI. The SPBE Index of National Development shows a consistent increase from 1.98 in 2018 to 2.34 in 2022, reflecting progressive efforts in implementing electronic governance frameworks. This trend aligns with the EGDI improvements in the same period, where the EGDI value rose from 0.5258 in 2018 to 0.7160 in 2022. The increase in SPBE sub-indices, particularly in the Policy Domain (from 1.75 in 2018 to 2.39 in 2022) and Services Domain (from 2.17 in 2018 to 2.96 in 2022), highlights targeted improvements in areas directly influencing EGDI metrics such as online services and e-participation.

These findings indicate that the SPBE initiatives have positively impacted Indonesia's global e-Government standing by addressing critical components measured by the EGDI. However, certain SPBE domains, such as Governance, have shown stagnation or slight

decreases (e.g., from 1.89 in 2021 to 1.85 in 2022), suggesting areas for further improvement. This analysis supports the view that while SPBE initiatives are effectively driving EGDI enhancements, a balanced development across all SPBE domains is crucial to ensure sustained progress and higher international rankings in the future.

The description of initiatives implemented by the Indonesian government, which have contributed to the improvement of SPBE and EGDI, is presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Trajectory initiatives of SPBE

Year	Description of initiatives and developments per year
2018	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enactment of Presidential Decree no. 59 of 2018 concerning SPBE which subsequently became the main reference for institutional digital transformation. - Enactment of Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation No. 5 of 2018 concerning monitoring and evaluation of SPBE. - Established regulations regarding guidelines for preparing business process maps through Permenpan RB No. 19 of 2018 which is the foundation for standardizing bureaucratic reform in government institutions. - Socialization of SPBE governance and monitoring and evaluation processes to all IPPD involving five universities in Indonesia.
2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National launch of SPBE to accelerate institutional digital transformation, especially in service and infrastructure management.
2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enactment of Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform Regulation No. 95 of 2020 concerning updated monitoring and evaluation of SPBE. - Establishment of SPBE risk management guidelines based on Permenpan RB No. 5 of 2020. - Establishment of regulations regarding SPBE data management based on Minister of PPN/Bapenas Regulation No. 16 of 2020.
2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establishment of a national SPBE coordination team through Kemenpan RB No. 963 of 2021. - Assisting to IPPD based on the results of Tauval 2020 which involves more campuses. - Establishment of SPBE information security management guidelines through BSSN Regulation No. 4 of 2021. - Released general applications that can be used by IPPD along with their achievement levels.
2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enactment of Presidential Decree on National SPBE Architecture No. 132 of 2022 as a reference and reference for the entire IPPD architecture. - Require IPPD Tauval with the predicate "Sufficient" and carry out new evaluations for 103 IPPDs that have not been evaluated. - Providing IPPD assistance with a good reputation in the pilot Smart City development project.

5. Discussion

The findings of this study provide a comprehensive understanding of how the Indonesian government has implemented e-Government initiatives and how these efforts are reflected in the improvements in the EGDI. Addressing the first research question, the initiatives implemented, such as the SPBE framework and associated regulations like Presidential Decree No. 95 of 2018, have laid a strong foundation for institutional digital transformation. The establishment of the SPBE governance structure, including key roles such as Chief Information Officer (CIO) and Chief Technology Officer (CTO), has streamlined

digital transformation processes across governmental institutions. These initiatives have enhanced the operational and service delivery capabilities of the Indonesian government, aligning with findings from institutional theory studies (e.g., Wahid & Sein, 2014).

In response to the second research question, the study highlights that the EGDI in Indonesia is measured based on the Online Service Index (OSI), Telecommunication Infrastructure Index (TII), and Human Capital Index (HCI). These indices are directly influenced by the SPBE's policy, governance, management, and services domains. For instance, improvements in the Services Domain of the SPBE, which increased from 2.17 in 2018 to 2.96 in 2022, significantly contributed to the OSI enhancements, as corroborated by the United Nations e-Government Survey (2022).

The third research question explores the relationship between SPBE measurement indicators and EGDI. The study reveals a positive correlation between SPBE maturity levels and EGDI scores. The maturity in SPBE's Policy and Services Domains, in particular, has a notable impact on EGDI components. For example, the strategic implementation of public service applications under the SPBE framework aligns with increased E-Participation Index values, as evidenced by a rise in rank from 92 in 2018 to 37 in 2022. This relationship underscores the role of well-structured e-Government frameworks in influencing global benchmarks like the EGDI (Rusmini et al., 2024).

Finally, institutional theory provides a robust lens for interpreting the influence of SPBE initiatives on EGDI improvements, addressing the fourth research question. Institutional isomorphism explains how coercive pressures, such as compliance with international standards, and mimetic practices, like benchmarking against successful e-Government systems, have driven SPBE adoption. Institutional logic highlights the role of cultural and normative factors in embedding digital transformation into bureaucratic practices. Furthermore, institutional entrepreneurship within key government agencies has catalyzed these changes, as demonstrated by proactive leadership in developing national e-Government policies. This aligns with the theoretical perspectives of DiMaggio & Powell (1983) and Scott (2014), who emphasize the interplay of institutional dynamics in organizational transformation.

6. Conclusions

This study highlights the significant role of Indonesia's SPBE initiatives in advancing the country's e-government development as reflected in the EGDI improvements between 2018 and 2022. By aligning SPBE domains—policy, governance, management, and services—with EGDI metrics such as the Online Service Index (OSI), Telecommunication Infrastructure Index (TII), and Human Capital Index (HCI), Indonesia has achieved measurable progress in its digital transformation efforts. The consistent increase in SPBE and EGDI scores underscores the effectiveness of the institutional reforms and the integration of digital solutions in public service delivery.

The application of institutional theory provides deeper insights into the mechanisms driving these improvements. Institutional isomorphism reveals the influence of normative, coercive, and mimetic forces in standardizing e-government practices. Institutional logic illustrates the growing awareness and responsibility for ICT-based bureaucratic reform, while institutional entrepreneurship demonstrates the critical role of leadership and innovation in accelerating digital transformation.

Despite these advancements, the findings also reveal areas requiring further attention, particularly in governance aspects of SPBE, which showed stagnation in recent years. Addressing these challenges is essential to sustaining progress and ensuring balanced development across all SPBE domains. Moreover, fostering collaboration between central and local governments can enhance the reach and impact of e-government initiatives.

This research not only contributes to the academic discourse on e-government development but also offers practical implications for policymakers aiming to optimize digital governance. Future studies could explore regional disparities in SPBE implementation and incorporate diverse stakeholder perspectives to build a more inclusive and comprehensive understanding of e-government dynamics in Indonesia and beyond.

References

- Aksom, H., & Tymchenko, I. (2020). How institutional theories explain and fail to explain organizations. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*, 33(7), 1223–1252. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JOCM-05-2019-0130>
- Aldrich, H., & Ruef, M. (2006). *Organizations Evolving*. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781446212509>
- Andersen, K. V., & Henriksen, H. Z. (2006). E-government maturity models: Extension of the Layne and Lee model. *Government Information Quarterly*, 23(2), 236–248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2005.11.008>
- Chizema, A., & Kim, J. (2010). Outside Directors on Korean Boards: Governance and Institutions. *Journal of Management Studies*, 47(1), 109–129. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2009.00868.x>
- Chizema, A., & Pogrebna, G. (2019). The impact of government integrity and culture on corporate leadership practices: Evidence from the field and the laboratory. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 30(5), 101303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2019.07.001>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design, Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (Fourth Edi). SAGE Publication.
- DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The Iron Cage Revisited: Institutional Isomorphism and Collective Rationality in Organizational Fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2095101>
- Edmunds, H. (1999). The Focus Group Research Handbook. *The Bottom Line*, 12(3), 46–46. <https://doi.org/10.1108/bl.1999.12.3.46.1>
- El gohary, E. M. (2017). E-government Implementation in Developing Countries: A Literature Review. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTERS & TECHNOLOGY*, 16(1), 7510–7524. <https://doi.org/10.24297/ijct.v16i1.8371>
- Frumkin, P. (2004). Institutional Isomorphism and Public Sector Organizations. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 14(3), 283–307. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/muh028>
- Grönlund, Å., & Horan, T. A. (2005). Introducing e-Gov: History, Definitions, and Issues. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 15. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.01539>
- ISACA. (2012). *COBIT 5 : a business framework for the governance and management of enterprise IT*. ISACA.
- Kim, D., & Grant, G. (2010). E-government maturity model using the capability maturity model integration. *Journal of Systems and Information Technology*, 12(3), 230–244. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13287261011070858>

- Klein, H. K., & Myers, M. D. (1999). A Set of Principles for Conducting and Evaluating Interpretive Field Studies in Information. *MIS Quarterly*, 23(1), 67–93.
- Layne, K., & Lee, J. (2001). Developing fully functional E-government: A four stage model. *Government Information Quarterly*, 18(2), 122–136. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0740-624X\(01\)00066-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0740-624X(01)00066-1)
- Meyer, J., & Rowan, B. (2011). Institutionalized Organizations: Formal Structure as Myth and Ceremony (translated by Igor Chirikov). *Journal of Economic Sociology*, 12(1), 43–67. <https://doi.org/10.17323/1726-3247-2011-1-43-67>
- Rachmawati, T., & Dwi Fitriyanti, K. (2021). Analysis of the E-Government Initiative at Local Government Level in Bandung City, Indonesia. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Ilmu Politik*, 25(1), 62. <https://doi.org/10.22146/jsp.58966>
- Rusmini, R., Alamsah Delarnoor, N., Yani Yuningsih, N., & Indrowati Sagita, N. (2024). E-Government and Public Services in Indonesia: Prospects and Challenges. *KnE Social Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v9i7.15507>
- Sabani, A. (2021). Investigating the influence of transparency on the adoption of e-Government in Indonesia. *Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management*, 12(2), 236–255. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSTPM-03-2020-0046>
- Scott, W. R. (2001). *Institutions and Organizations*. SAGE Publications.
- Scott, W. R. (2014). Institutions and Organizations. Ideas, Interests and Identities. *M@n@gement*, 17(2), 136. <https://doi.org/10.3917/mana.172.0136>
- Thornton, P. H., Ocasio, W., & Lounsbury, M. (2015). The Institutional Logics Perspective. In *Emerging Trends in the Social and Behavioral Sciences* (pp. 1–22). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118900772.etrds0187>
- UN-DESA Survey. (2022). *E-Government Survey 2022 The Future of Digital Government*. <https://publicadministration.un.org/en/>
- Wahid, F., & Sein, M. K. (2013). Institutional entrepreneurs: The driving force in institutionalization of public systems in developing countries. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 7(1), 76–92. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17506161311308179>
- Wahid, F., & Sein, M. K. (2014). Steering Institutionalization through Institutional Work: The Case of an eProcurement System in Indonesian Local Government. *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, 4264–4274. <https://doi.org/10.1109/HICSS.2014.527>
- Wijaya, J. H. (2023). E-Government in Indonesia: Policy Review and Implementation of Jokowi's Government. *TheJournalish: Social and Government*, 4(3), 302–309. <https://doi.org/10.55314/tsg.v4i3.563>